

INFANT MORTALITY RATE AND PUBLIC HEALTH CARE IN NIGERIA (2000-2022)

GRACE PAULINUS JIM, Ph.D

**Department of Physical and Health Education, Faculty of Education,
University of Uyo**

&

FRIDAY EYO UKO

Department of Economics, University of Uyo, Uyo

Email: friday_uko@yahoo.com

Abstract

The study examined the relationship between infant mortality rate and public health care in Nigeria for the period 2000-2022. Specifically, the study examined the relationship between health education, adequate nutrition, safe water and sanitation and infant mortality rate. The study employed an ex-post facto design and data for the selected variables were obtained from UNICEF data set and World Development Indicators data sets. The relationship between the variables was determined using ordinary Least Square Estimation Technique in linear form. Findings from the estimated models showed that a negative and significant relationship exist between health education and infant mortality rate; a negative and non-significant relationship between adequate nutrition and infant mortality rate; a positive and significant relationship between sanitation and infant mortality rate and a negative and significant relationship between safe water and infant mortality rate. In view of the findings, it was concluded that, proper health education, safe water, good sanitation practice and adequate nutrition can help to reduce the rate of infant mortality in Nigeria. It was therefore recommended that, proper health education should be given to pregnant and breastfeeding women during ante-natal, neo-natal and post-natal period. Furthermore, individuals and communities should make sanitation a continuous practice.

Keywords: Infant Mortality Rate, Health Education; Public Health, Primary Health Care.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable Development Goal (SGD) 3 includes a target to “achieve universal health coverage (UHC), including financial risk protection, access to quality essential health care services, and access to safe, effective, quality, and affordable essential medicines and vaccines for all. To achieve this goal, there has been a call for health reforms, reappraisal of priorities, and pragmatically aligning health policies. In Nigeria, the efforts of government are geared toward the revitalization of primary health care (PHC), with a special focus on poor and vulnerable populations; an expansion of the insurance base; and the implementation of integrated primary health

care systems, through the reduction of fragmentation of government institutions responsible for PHC governance and leadership (Odutolu *et al.*, 2016).

The national health policy regards primary health care as the framework to achieve improved health for the population. Primary health care services include health education; adequate nutrition; safe water and sanitation; reproductive health, including family planning; immunisation against five major infectious diseases; the provision of essential drugs; and disease control. Infant and childhood mortality rates are good index to measure the health and socio-economic status of a nation. In most developing countries today, mortality is higher at infancy than any other age groups. The infant mortality rate of 75/000 and childhood mortality of 98/000 and maternal mortality of 545/100000 births is unacceptable. These high rates could be attributable to worsening socio-economic situation in the country and the failure of health programmes and interventions (Chinedu and Azuh, 2017; WHO, 2017).

The National Primary Health Care Development Agency (NPHCDA) provides support for the implementation of the National Health Policy in all matters relating to primary health care (PHC) in Nigeria. Within the policy, PHC is identified as the 'main focus for delivering effective, efficient, quality, accessible and affordable health services to a wider proportion of the population'. Subsequent to this mandate, one of its core functions is the development of effective systems of supervision, monitoring and evaluation of PHC based on national guidelines and standards.

Ideally, Primary health care (PHC) is the foundation of the health care system. For most Nigerians, PHC is the first point of contact with the health care system. It is the level at which short-term, uncomplicated health issues should be resolved. It is also the level at which health promotion and education efforts are undertaken, and where patients in need of more specialized services are connected with secondary care. The four basic approaches to PHC in Nigeria are to: (i) Promote community participation in planning, management, monitoring and evaluation; (ii) Improve inter-sectoral collaboration in primary health care delivery; (iii) Enhance functional integration at all levels of the health system and (iv) strengthen managerial processes for health development at all levels (FGN, 2012).

The introduction of the Ward Health System was a culmination of efforts to provide an appropriate infra-structural resource for support and co-management of viable community based integrated PHC services through the provision of a minimum package of equipment, drugs and other supplies for PHC. This system requires smaller subgroups of health facilities to cater for areas that are far from the ward health centre but within the same ward. Unfortunately, systemic weaknesses and long-term neglect have made the ideal impossible to achieve in the short term, hence the need for defining and declaring a set of Minimum Standards especially in the areas of health infrastructure, human and financial resources and provision of essential drugs and commodities for primary health institutions in Nigeria.

The state of the Nigeria children today is very worrisome. A large number of children are dying thereby putting into question the various health and population policies of the government. Infant and childhood mortality rates are good indices to measure the health and socio-economic status of any society. Generally speaking, infant and childhood mortality rates in Nigeria are on the decline as recorded by various National Demographic and Health Surveys, but it is still high by world standard. This contrasts sharply with the abundant human and natural resources available in the country. Unfortunately, poverty, ignorance, environmental hazards, and uneven distribution of government amenities, especially health services have been the bane of development planning in Nigeria. While a lot of poverty alleviation/eradication programmes are mounted by the government their impact are hardly felt and poverty rate has ever been on the increase. Poverty is one of the most important determining factors of childhood mortality. It also impacts negatively on health care utilization such that its reduction is a goal that must be achieved. The primary health care system is adopted in the country to address the challenges in infant/childcare, maternal/reproductive health and make family planning available to wide spectrum of Nigeria population. Ironically the primary health care system failed to meet its target or objectives.

Health systems around the globe still fall short of providing accessible, good-quality, comprehensive and integrated care. As the global health community is setting ambitious goals of universal health coverage and health equity in line with the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, there is increasing interest in access to and utilization of primary health care in low- and middle-income countries. A wide array of stakeholders, including development agencies, global health funders, policy planners and health system decision-makers, require a better understanding of primary health care systems in order to plan and support complex health system interventions. There is thus a need to fill the knowledge gaps concerning strategic information on front-line primary health care systems at national and sub-national levels in low- and middle-income settings.

As expected, this study seeks to examine the impact of PHC system on infant mortality rate; know the trend of infant and childhood mortality rates; identify determinants of infant/childhood mortality and how PHC can be effectively managed to ensure infant natality.

The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of primary health care (PHC) on infant mortality rate in Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- i. Examine the impact of health education on infant mortality rate.
- ii. Examine the impact of adequate nutrition on infant mortality rate
- iii. Examine the impact of safe water on infant mortality rate.
- iv. Examine the impact sanitation on infant mortality rate.

Based on the above objectives, the following research questions therefore arises:

- i. What impact does health education have on infant mortality rate?

- ii. What impact does adequate nutrition have on infant mortality rate?
- iii. What impact does safe water have on infant mortality rate?
- iv. What impact does sanitation have on infant mortality rate?

The following null hypotheses will be tested:

Ho: Health Education has no significant impact on infant mortality rate.

Ho: Adequate nutrition has no significant impact on infant mortality rate.

Ho: Safe water has no significant impact on infant mortality rate

Ho: Sanitation has no significant impact on infant mortality rate

Health of citizens of a country implies the wealth of such nation. This study is expected to provide an overview of the primary healthcare system, tailored to a primary audience of policymakers and global health stakeholders interested in understanding the key entry points to strengthening primary health care systems. The comprehensive case study provides an in-depth assessment of the system for an audience of researchers and stakeholders who wish to gain deeper insight into the determinants and performance of primary health care systems in Nigeria. In a society like Nigeria where every death is attributed to superstition, it is expected that this study will allay such belief and point out that death especially in infant is inevitable with poor hygiene and nutrition besides poor health education and reproductive health.

Furthermore, the case study will serve as the basis for a multi-country analysis of primary health care systems, focusing on the implementation of policies and programmes, and the barriers to and facilitators of primary health care system reform. Evidence from the case studies and the multi-country analysis will in turn provide strategic evidence to enhance the performance and responsiveness of primary healthcare systems in low- and middle-income countries.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Issues

2.1.1 Primary Health Care

Primary health care was defined at the 1978 Declaration of Alma-Ata as: [E]ssential health care based on practical, scientifically sound and socially acceptable methods and technology made universally accessible to individuals and families in the community through their full participation and at a cost that the community and country can afford to maintain at every stage of their development in the spirit of self-reliance and self-determination (Oyekale, 2017: Oluwole et al, 2022). Primary health care is the first point of contact for health services provision and a point of entry for the entire health system. Research has shown that access to PHC services is linked to better health outcomes. Hence access to PHC in the LMICs also hinges on the availability and readiness of the primary health centres. Primary health centres in the context of LMICs address geographical access and provide comprehensive services to the population, often with both curative and preventive components.

One of the main functions of a health system is to ensure access to quality health services. Different components of service access include availability, affordability and acceptability (Ekenna et al, 2020) Service availability denotes the physical existence of the delivery of services and incorporates health infrastructure, core health personnel and aspects of service utilisation. Service affordability refers to how the service provider's charges correspond to the client's ability and willingness to pay for services, whilst service acceptability refers to the extent to which the client is comfortable with the more incommutable characteristics of the provider and vice versa. These characteristics include the age, gender, social class and ethnicity of the provider (and of the client), including the diagnosis and type of coverage of the client.

Service readiness, which is a prerequisite for service quality, is defined as the availability of mechanisms required to provide services in five domains that denote general service readiness. This refers to the overall capacity of health facilities to offer general health services that include possession of basic amenities, basic equipment, standard precautions for infection prevention, diagnostic capacity and essential medicines. On the other hand, specific-service readiness denotes the ability of health facilities to provide a particular service, and the ability to provide such service is measured through consideration of some tracer items which include trained staff, guidelines, equipment, diagnostic capacity, medicines and commodities

Nigeria operates a three-tiered health care delivery system, with a large percentage of health care delivery vested at the PHC level. The government has continued its efforts to decentralise healthcare services to the PHC centres to ensure that health services are located closer to the people and are also more affordable. This is expected to lead to the improvement of a wide range of health indices that affect the quality of life of the citizens. Primary health care was adopted in the 1988 National Health Policy as the cornerstone of the Nigerian health system as part of efforts to improve equity in access and utilisation of basic health services. Since then, PHC in Nigeria has evolved through various stages of development (Aigiromelen *et al.*, 2014). In Nigeria, as well as other LMICs, huge gaps in the capacity and delivery of basic clinical care have been documented, as well as poor quality care, including poor care by health care providers (Okonofua *et al.*, 2018; Ntoimo *et al.*, 2019). All these contribute to poor utilisation of PHC facilities amongst the public. It has been documented in Nigeria that PHC centres are poorly utilised, leading to failure to meet the goals of UHC (Oyekale, 2017).

At primary healthcare (PHC) level in Nigeria, community health workers who are in paid employment comprise mainly community health officers (CHO), community health extension workers (CHEWs) and junior community health workers (JCHEWs). These types of frontline healthcare workers, with strong ties to the community, are less likely to be influenced by the dynamics of international health

labour markets—thus less likely to engage in inter-country health workforce migration. About 99% of maternal, newborn and child deaths occur within developing countries. Nigeria which is the most populous country within sub-Saharan Africa, similarly has poor maternal, newborn and child mortality indices (Okereke *et al.*, 2019).

According to the National Guidelines for the development of primary healthcare systems in Nigeria, the JCHEWs are expected to provide basic and essential community services with guidance from standing orders as well as spend about 90% of their time working within the community. The community health functions of JCHEWs include ensuring the community's participation in health-related activities, conducting home and community visits, clients' follow-up and identifying and registering pregnant women for antenatal care and support. The CHEWs according to the National Guidelines have similar functions as the JCHEWs but are expected to spend about 40% of their time working in the community and more time working within health facilities, promoting preventive maternal and child healthcare and managing clients according to standing orders (Okereke *et al.*, 2019).

There is evidence that community health workers contribute towards the delivery of maternal, newborn and child health (MNCH) services such as childhood immunization, antenatal care and facility-based deliveries within PHC settings (Kok *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, the implementation of the task shifting and sharing policy has empowered many community health workers, through training and capacity building, to acquire skills which are crucial for promoting maternal, newborn and child health in Nigeria (Adebayo, Okereke and Joseph, 2019). However, there is limited evidence about the performance of community health workers vis-a-vis maternal, newborn and child health service delivery in Nigeria. As a result, it is difficult for policymakers to ascertain what specific changes to the health workforce maybe required to significantly improve health outcomes.

2.1.2 Infant Mortality Rate

Infant mortality (IM) is the death of an infant before his or her first birthday. Infant mortality rate (IMR) is a key indicator of the overall health of a society and is essential for social and economic development (Shobiye *et al.*, 2022). According to Okwuwa and Adejo (2020), Infant mortality rate symbolizes a measure of a country's health policy, systems and practices, an aspect of its national development. It is often associated with socio-economic factors of unemployment, poverty, income disparity, among others, in a polity. Infant and maternal challenges should be contextualized in overall national development policies and practices. High rates of infant and maternal mortality express low social integration of children and women. It symbolizes low female gender participation and inclusion in socio-economic processes. Nigerian women generally lack the power to determine child spacing,

access and choice of modern healthcare, among others. This is a denial of women human rights, and remotely, children's survival rights and a backward step towards high birth and death rates.

Infant mortality has become more prevalent due to lack of access to health care before, during and after delivery. This contributes to high infant mortality rates both in developing and under-developed country (WHO, 2017). Okwuwa and Adejo (2020, observe that, every day, Nigeria loses about 2,300 under-five year olds and 145 women of child-bearing age, making the country the second largest contributor to under-five and maternal mortality rate in the world. Many lives can be saved if global inequalities are reduced (UNICEF, 2017). Today, 89,700, day-old babies die in Nigeria yearly (State of the World's Mother's, 2016). Nigeria has the 12th highest rate of first day deaths in the world, making it one of the riskiest places to be born. Nigeria is one of the ten countries with highest infant mortality rates in Africa (UNICEF, 2016). Nigeria ranked 152nd out of 176 countries and among the 10 worst countries to be a pregnant woman or a child (Save the Children International, 2016).

Essieumoh *et al.* (2021), observe that Mothers and their newborns constitute vulnerable groups in the population with regard to health. Globally, high rates of maternal and neonatal mortality have been reported. Most recent global data show an estimated maternal mortality ratio of 211/100,000 live births with about 295,000 maternal deaths (WHO *et al.*, 2019a). Data also revealed that 5.4 million children under five years old died in 2017 (WHO, 2018). These phenomena have a higher occurrence in the developing world than in the industrialized areas. In the developing world, sub-Saharan Africa and southern Asia are most affected. World Health Organization (WHO) revealed that at country level, Nigeria in sub-Saharan Africa and India in south Asia had the highest number of estimated maternal deaths and accounted for about one third (35%) of these deaths in 2017. Specifically, Nigeria accounted for approximately 67,000 (23%) and India, 35,000 (12%) global maternal deaths (WHO *et al.*, 2019b). Neonatal and infant mortality also follow the trend of maternal mortality as the survival of neonates depends on maternal health (van den Broek, 2006). The burden of infant mortality is also greatest in sub-Saharan Africa and Nigeria has Infant mortality rate of 70/1000 live births (Joseph and Earland, 2019).

The causes of maternal and child morbidity and mortality have been found to relate to lack of skilled birth attendants. The use of antenatal and childbirth services provided by skilled attendants can result in significant reduction of maternal and newborn morbidities and mortality due to early detection of complications and prompt intervention (WHO *et al.*, 2010). Studies have shown that only about 35% of Nigerian women are attended by skilled birth attendants and that MNCH services are underutilized (Ronsmans and Graham, 2006, Ibekwe and Ibekwe, 2008, Okonofua *et al.*, 2011, WHO, 2011b). In recognition of this tragedy of high maternal and infant mortalities, maternal, newborn and child health (MNCH) service was designed to promote the health of mothers and children under five years of age. However, despite

this effort by the government, maternal and infant mortalities are still high in Nigeria as shown in WHO estimates (WHO et al., 2019a). Whereas, it has been observed that MNCH service is an effective strategy in reducing these deaths (Kuhut and Vollmer, 2017). The low demand for contemporary health services have been found to be consequent upon cultural beliefs and practices as well as lack of trust in the health care system (Archibong and Agan, 2010, Adegoke et al., 2010, Mboho *et al.*, 2013, Esienumoh *et al.*, 2018).

In the past two decades, many countries have achieved significant improvements in reducing IM. According to the UN 2018 mortality report, IMR declined by 51% between 2000 and 2017. Despite this progress, wide disparities exist between low-income and high-income countries—76 deaths per 1000 live births and 7 deaths per 1000 live births respectively.³ Nigeria reported 72 deaths per 1000 live births among infants in 2020 with disparities across its regions and geopolitical zones. Nigeria has worse IMR compared with neighboring West African countries such as Benin, Cameroon, Togo and Ghana, with 57, 48, 44 and 33 deaths per 1000 live births, respectively (World Bank, 2022; UNICEF, 2022)

The rate makes Nigeria one of the countries with the highest IMR rate in Africa. Studies show that there are several determinants of IM in Nigeria. In 2010, low birth weight was highlighted as the most common cause of IM accounting for 25% of IM.⁶ The study also identified lack of delivery attendants, home delivery and traditional birth attendants as predictors of IM in Nigeria. This is supported by Samantha Slinkard et al., (2018) who reported lack of access to Antenatal care (ANC) or delayed ANC initiation as an important risk factor for increased IM. (Lawoyin *et al.*, 2017).

According to the 2013 NDHS report, 34% of women did not receive ANC and only 18% of those who received ANC did so in the first trimester. Some factors are associated with this high IMR in Nigeria, such as age of mother, socioeconomic status and region which contribute to the impact of ANC initiation. Other factors highlighted include place of residence, child's sex, skill of birth attendant, delivery by caesarean operation, birth order, birth interval, maternal education, maternal age, and wealth index. Meanwhile, Nigeria has implemented several interventions and policies to improve IMR. An example is the Nigeria Midwives Service Scheme (MSS), a public sector collaborative initiative established in December 2009 by the National Primary Health Care Development Agency (NPHCDA). However, despite these interventions and policies, IMR in Nigeria remains high—the 4th highest in Sub-Saharan Africa as of 2020 (Adedeni et al, 2015). As Nigeria continues to grapple with the burden of infant mortality, child survival remains an urgent concern.

Often, the mortality is related to the antenatal condition of the women—such as pregnancy hypertension, preeclampsia, and anemia—that may complicate preterm births and affect the survival of the baby. These ante-natal conditions mentioned above emphasize the need to address social determinants of IM in the country.

Addressing these factors would therefore require a strong design and implementation of targeted, innovative, and sustainable health interventions.

The United Nations Population Fund (UNPF) (2019) observes that Nigeria's population is 201 million, with average growth rate of 2.6 percent from 2010 to 2019, meaning that an average Nigerian woman gives birth to at least five children, against global 2.5 percent in 2019. The report states: Contraceptive prevalence rate among Nigerian women aged 15-49 is only 19 percent, decision-making on sexual and reproductive health and reproductive rights among these women averaged 51 percent between 2007 and 2018. This symbolizes women marginalization, powerlessness and exclusion in the Nigerian social structure and governance processes. It functionally reflects two worlds; the decision-making, superior and more mentally developed men's world and the deprived, depraved, inferior and low mentally created women's world, a near master servant social construct, immanent, and beyond re-ordering. This is a retardant to human and national development.

This can partly be explained by rooted cultural practices, including primordial skepticism on western education and culture, religious observances that limit expectant mothers' ante and post-natal behavioral choices on food and drug intake, activities of traditional birth attendants and absence of trained healthcare service providers particularly in rural areas. Porter (2017) opines that 3 million children need emergency education support in North-East Nigeria. The UNICEF (2017) notes that poverty, low children school attendance, maternal mortality and low-level development are more in the North than in the South of Nigeria. Logically, infant mortality can be holistically addressed with well-organized regular immunization, daycare and preparatory education, under government regulation.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The study is based on social action theory. The theory of social action was proposed by a German Sociologist Max Weber (1864–1920) in 1922. The theory of social action looks at the reaction between a stimulus and the ultimate response. In his action theory, Weber tried to analyze the action of individuals in typical situations. He saw the need to understand and interpret human behavior based on the meanings behind their actions. That is, understanding human behavior and the reasons behind such behaviors.

Interactionist sociologists believe that social structures and institutions are not the primary drivers or determinants of social behaviour. People play a much proactive role in shaping their social life. The pregnant woman plays active roles in determining if she would present for maternal healthcare services or not. Most people engage in voluntary behaviour because they have free will. Maternal healthcare services and maternal mortality among women is based on the free will of women to utilize maternal healthcare services. The social action theory advanced that although people operate as individuals, nevertheless the attitudes and actions of other people around them influence the way they think and the way they behave at the household,

individual, and community level. When there is a high use of maternal healthcare services, mothers will be influenced to use ante-natal, natal, and post-natal healthcare services. People acquire knowledge about appropriate behaviour in particular situations, social responses are elicited in particular contexts. The pregnant mother has learnt what constitutes appropriate behaviour on the use or non-utilization of maternal healthcare services (Arisukwu *et al.*, 2021).

Community level factors through symbolic interaction teaches what constitutes appropriate maternal health behaviour in a community where emphasis is on the use of ante-natal, natal, and post-natal maternal healthcare services. Pregnant women are more likely to make themselves available for maternal healthcare services. The direction of use of maternal healthcare services in a community is also an important indicator of how pregnant women would use maternal healthcare services, if the emphasis at the household or community level is on the preference of local birth attendants, the tendency for expectant women to patronize traditional birth attendants becomes high. Society evolves when people interact in social groups and make sense of each other behaviour, role and norms exist in all societies, but they are flexible guidelines rather than unchangeable frameworks over which we have no control, whatever the role an individual plays in the society is open to negotiation and individual interpretation. The pregnant women can have acquired social entities in the process of socialization, the socialization shows what the society expects those in a particular role to live up to. Pregnant mothers are expected to utilize maternal healthcare services in some socio-cultural environment, while in others, a social identity of utilization of Maternal Healthcare Services may not be important.

2.3 Empirical Review

Okereke *et al.* (2019) assessed stakeholders' perceptions about the performance of community health workers and the feasibility of introducing and using community midwifery to address the high maternal and newborn mortality within the Nigerian healthcare system. The Study Utilised a qualitative research design where interviews were conducted with 44 purposively selected key informants. Key informants were selected based on their knowledge and experience working with different cadres of frontline health workers at primary healthcare level. The qualitative data were audio-recorded, transcribed and then thematically analysed. The study revealed that, introducing community midwifery will increase access to maternal and newborn healthcare services, especially in rural communities. Furthermore, it was found that applying community midwifery at the primary healthcare level may lead to duplication of duties among the health worker cadres, possibly creating disharmony. Some key informants suggested that there should be concerted efforts to train and retrain the existing cadres of community health workers via the effective implementation of the task shifting policy in Nigeria, in addition to possibly revising the existing training curricula, instead of introducing community midwifery.

Okwuwa and Adejo (2020) examined Nigeria's critical dimensions of infant mortality and access to primary health centers (PHCs) as behavioral tendencies

capable of shaping the present and future of infancy, childhood, the family and the nation, using Bwari community as a case study. The research employed qualitative and quantitative methods with testable hypotheses. Findings revealed that respondents' socio-economic characteristics intermediate on extent of accessing available health care facilities. The respondents' relatively high literacy, urban residency and civil service jobs, health talks from medical professionals, free medical treatment and, very importantly, zero infant mortality outcome, suggest that environment, human capital quality and health outcomes have relationships.

Abuqamar, Coomans and Louckx (2020) determined the relationship between educational level of parents and infant mortality in the Gaza strip. Face to face interviews were carried out on 550 mothers of infants (275 dead infants and 275 live births) in the Gaza strip. Binary logistic regression analyses were used to identify the relationship between health behavioral factors and infant mortality. The result of the study showed that the families with lower educational level had a much higher risk of infant mortality. There was a positive statistical association between parental education and survival of infants. The findings underscore the importance of explicit attention to health education.

Raghupathi and Raghupathi (2020) explored the association between education and health over a 20-year period for countries around the world. Using empirical data from the OECD and the World Bank for 26 OECD countries for the years 1995–2015, the study identified patterns/associations between education and health indicators. By incorporating pre- and post-educational attainment indicators, the study highlighted the dual role of education as both a driver of opportunity as well as of inequality. The result of the study showed that, adults with higher educational attainment have better health and life spans compared to their less educated peers. It was further highlighted that tertiary education, particularly, is critical in influencing infant mortality, life expectancy, child vaccination, and enrollment rates. In addition, an economy needs to consider potential years of life lost (premature mortality) as a measure of health quality.

Esienumoh *et al.* (2021) examined how mothers utilize the services in a tertiary and a cluster of Primary Health Care facilities. Qualitative case study design was used and participants were selected through purposive sampling. Data were generated through twenty-three in-depth personal interviews of mothers and three focus group discussions with healthcare providers. Following thematic data analysis, the following five themes emerged: (1) mothers' awareness of available maternal and child health services, (2) maternal satisfaction with services, (3) factors influencing mothers' continuity with utilization, (4) motivators for service utilization, (5) barriers to service utilization. Family, trust in health providers and self-determination motivated service utilization. Barriers to utilization included consumers' issue such as ignorance, fear of caesarean section and superstitious beliefs; systemic issues for example, high cost and infrastructural problems; providers' issues like poor relational attitudes, undue delay in service delivery and staff shortage; cultural/religious issues

including influence of traditional birth attendants and Church. The study concluded that utilization of maternal and child health services is inconsistent; thus, mothers and their children are predisposed to morbidity and mortality

Okonofua *et al.* (2022) determined the effectiveness of a set of multifaceted interventions designed to increase the access of rural women to antenatal, intrapartum, postpartum and childhood immunisation services offered in primary healthcare facilities in Esan South East and Etsako East Local Government Areas in Edo State in southern Nigeria. The study was a separate sample pretest–post- test quasi- experimental research. The research was conducted in 20 communities and primary health centres. The outcome measures included the number of women who used the primary health centres for skilled pregnancy care and immunisation of children aged 0–23 months. After adjusting for clustering and confounding variables, the odds of using the project primary healthcare centres for the four outcomes were significantly higher at endline compared with baseline: antenatal care, delivery care, postnatal care and childhood immunisation. However, a few women still reported that the cost of services and gender- related issues were reasons for non- use after the intervention. The study concluded that community- led interventions that address the specific concerns of women related to the bottlenecks they experience in accessing care in primary health centres are effective in increasing demand for skilled pregnancy and childcare in rural Nigeria.

Oluwole *et al.* (2022) assessed maternal and child health (MCH) services' specific readiness by type and location of the health facility and compared the readiness between urban and rural primary health care (PHC) facilities in Ekiti State, Nigeria. A descriptive cross-sectional study in which all PHC facilities were conducted and data were collected with the aid of the Service Availability and Readiness Assessment (SARA) tool using the Kobo Collect app. Data were cleaned and coded on Microsoft Excel 2016 and exported to Stata SE 12 for analysis. Findings showed that, Health facilities located in urban areas had more medicines and commodities compared with those of rural areas.

Shobiye *et al.* (2022), conducted a population-level study using the 2018 Nigeria Demographic Health Survey (NDHS). A total of 41,668 household data were analyzed retrospectively. The association between each exposure and infant mortality was analyzed in logistic regression models (independently adjusted by demographic and socioeconomic status variables) and confirmed by the multiple comparisons analysis. Finding showed that the overall IMR of 2013–2017 was 61.5 per 1000 live births. In general, the North-West and North-East regions had the highest IMR, whereas the South-West, South-East and South-South regions had the lowest IMR. The regression analysis found women who delivered their babies at the age ≤ 18 years old, had religion of Islam, no ANC visit > 4 ANC visits, ANC not at home or skilled provider and the babies as the first child to be associated with higher IMR. Interpretation of the findings imply that Nigeria is not on track to achieving the SDG target of reducing child mortality by 2030. Sustainable interventions are

urgently needed to address the challenges for women of reproductive age, particularly those that are living in the rural areas and Northern regions, having limited/no access to health care/ skilled providers, and delivered their first child.

Islam *et al.* (2022), investigated the prevalence of infant mortality and assess how different factors influence infant mortality in 24 developing countries by utilising the latest Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) data. The study used a mixed-method design to assemble cross-sectional studies to integrate data from 24 other countries due to the widening perspective of infant mortality. Descriptive analysis, binary logistic regression model, random-effect meta-analysis and forest plot were used for the analyses. The binary logistic regression model for Bangladesh revealed that a higher education level of fathers, being 2nd born or above order infant, undergoing antenatal care and undergoing postnatal care (PNC) were statistically significant determinants of lowering infant death. While carrying multiple fetuses was shown to be a risk factor of infant mortality. The most significant factors influencing infant mortality for developing countries were the number of foetuses, undergoing ANC, undergoing PNC and the size of the children. The study concluded that, the number of the foetuses, undergoing ANC and PNC, mother's education, fathers' education and size of the children were the most significant factors affecting infant mortality in developing countries.

2.4 Summary of literature reviewed

Infant mortality no doubt is a big problem plaguing Nigeria as a country. From the review it is glaring that various factors are responsible for growing rate of infant mortality. It should also be mentioned that none of the study has clearly pointed out the place of nutrition, sanitation and water as factors contributing to growing infant mortality. This study seeks to fill this gap.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Design of Study

The study adopts an ex-post facto design. The ex-post facto design is based on the available information. This makes it rather impossible for the information to be manipulated by the researcher.

3.2 Variable of Study

The variables of study are primary health care and infant mortality rate. Infant mortality rate is the dependent variable while primary health care is the independent variable.

3.3 Variable description and measurement

Infant mortality rate is the number of children who dies before their first birthday. It is measured by the number of death per thousand births. Primary health care is the first level of health contact and it is measured by percentage of population that has access to maternal care, access to water and sanitation, nutrition among others.

3.4 Sources of Data

Data for the identified variables was obtained from UNICEF data set and World Development Indicators data base for the year 2000-2022.

3.5 Model Specification

From the identified variables and in line with the objectives of the study, the model is specified as;

$$IMR = f(PhC) \quad (1)$$

Given that PhC consists of health education, nutrition, sanitation, and water, equation (1) can be modeled as;

$$IMR = f(Hyg, Nt, Snt, Wat) \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) implies that infant mortality rate is influenced by health education proxied by hygiene, nutrition, sanitation and water.

To make (2) amendable for estimation, it can be presented as;

$$IMR = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 Hyg + \beta_2 Nt + \beta_3 Snt + \beta_4 Wat + \epsilon$$

Where; IMR = infant mortality rate; Nt = nutrition; Snt = sanitation; Wat = water; ϵ = error term.

Hyg = hygiene

The expectation is that if there is adequate nutrition, proper sanitation and washing of hand with water, the rate of infant mortality will reduce. Thus, the expected sign for Nt, Snt and Wat is negative.

3.6 Estimation Technique

The formulated model was estimated using ordinary Least Square estimation technique in linear form with the help of Eview 12.

4. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULT

In this section, the result of the relationship between dependent and independent variables are presented and analysed in line with the objectives of the study.

Table 4.1: Impact of Primary Health Care on Infant Mortality Rate

Variable	coefficient	Std. Error	t-stat	Prob.
C	303.6338	47.02198	6.457274	0.0000
HYG	-12.33293	4.530730	-2.722063	0.014
NUT	-0.084413	0.101627	-0.830614	0.4171
SAN	0.984723	0.297685	3.307937	0.0039
WAT	-1.620193	0.423202	-3.828419	0.0012
R2 = 0.80 Adj. R2 = 0.75 DW. = 1.64				

Source: Author's computation with Eview 12

The study sought to examine the impact of Primary Health care on Infant Mortality Rate. Primary health care comprises of health education proxied by hygiene which is the percentage of population using soap and water to wash their hands, adequate nutrition which is proxied by the rate of breastfeeding, sanitation proxied by percentage of population enjoying adequate sanitation and water which represent the percentage of population having access to clean water source.

Objectively, the study sought to;

Examine the impact of health education on infant mortality rate

Examine the impact of adequate nutrition on infant mortality rate

Examine the impact of safe water on infant mortality rate

Examine the impact of sanitation on infant mortality rate

From the Table 4.1 above, attempt is made to answer the following research questions;

Research Question one: What impact does health education have on infant mortality rate?

From the Table 4.1 above, it is observed that, health education which is proxied by hygiene has negative and significant impact on infant mortality rate. This finding is in line with the a priori expectation. This implies that proper hygiene by a nursing mother can reduce the rate of infant mortality.

Research Question Two: What impact does adequate nutrition have on infant mortality rate?

Going back to the Table 4.1, nutrition has negative non-significant impact on infant mortality rate. The negative sign is appropriate in view of the fact that proper nutrition of infant could help in reducing the rate of infant mortality.

Research Question Three: What impact does safe water have on infant mortality rate?

Again, the Table 4.1 indicates a negative significant relationship between safe water and infant mortality rate. The sign is appropriate. This is because, safe drinking water will reduce exposure to water borne bacteria that may likely cause infant death. Thus, with safe drinking water, rate of infant mortality will reduce.

Research Question Four: What impact does sanitation have on infant mortality rate?

From the Table 4.1, indicates that, sanitation has a positive significant impact on infant mortality rate. Though the sign is inappropriate, the fact that the relationship between sanitation and infant mortality rate is significant indicates that poor sanitary condition can trigger the rate of infant mortality while good sanitary condition could result in the opposite.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One: Health Education has no significant impact on infant mortality rate.

The result from the Table 4.1 shows that there is a significant relationship between health education and infant mortality rate. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Test of Hypothesis Two: Adequate nutrition has no significant impact on infant mortality rate.

The result of the relationship between adequate nutrition and infant mortality rate is non-significant. In view of this, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Test of Hypothesis Three: Safe water has no significant impact on infant mortality rate.

The result of the relationship between safe water and infant mortality rate is significant. On the basis of this, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Test of Hypothesis Four: Sanitation has no significant impact on infant mortality rate.

The result indicates a significant relationship. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

The study was undertaken with a view to examining the relationship between infant mortality rate and primary health care. Primary health care is essential for the socioeconomic growth of any nation. Though some countries have made efforts in reducing infant mortality rate, Nigeria still has the highest rate of infant mortality in Africa. This development has been attributed to cultural belief, poor health education, poor reproductive health training, poverty and religious belief among others. The present study has shown that a part from what had been believed to cause infant mortality, nutrition, sanitation, health education and water source contribute greatly to infant mortality rate. Judging by the four hypotheses used for this study, it can be deduced that, health education, safe water and sanitation has significant impact in the reduction of infant mortality rate in Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusion

Primary health care is vital for the growth and wellbeing of any nation. While the constitutional responsibility of providing primary health care rest with the Local Government authority, it is also important for individuals and other tier of government to promote this important component of the health sector by ensuring that proper health education is given to pregnant women and breastfeeding mothers so as to promote healthy living and proper management of minor health problems within the early years of a child. Apart from health education, water source should be safe and proper culture of environmental sanitation should be encouraged and promoted among residents.

5.3 Recommendations

From the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made;

1. Health education should be strictly practiced at the individual and community level. This practice should be particularly stressed during ante natal, neo natal and post-natal period in pregnant and breastfeeding mothers.
2. There should be collective effort both by the government and individuals to ensure provision of safe drinking water for private and public use. If possible, the government should go back to the era of public water system so that safe drinking water can as well be accessed by the poor.
3. Apart from the law enforcing sanitation exercise, individuals and at the community level should see sanitation as a way of life. This will help free the environment of disease-causing microbes.
4. Parents should be conscious of what they feed their infants. Apart from medical advice, parents are the closest people to their children and have the right to determine what form of nutrition is best suited for their infants.

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